

SHORT COMMUNICATION

Influence of seismic strain rates on the co- and post-seismic response of civil engineering buildings

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Summary

The elastic properties of buildings change during earthquakes. In particular, fundamental frequencies are observed to shift rapidly during the co-seismic phase and to recover slowly once the strong motion has finished. Although the frequency shift is usually correlated with loading amplitude, the co-seismic frequency variations observed in real structures are not only determined by the absolute amplitude of the strain value. In order to interpret the uncertainties of the prediction of engineering demand parameters for a given intensity measure, we analyze the influence of loading rates (i.e., strain rates) on resonance frequency variations in buildings with different structural states during the loading and unloading phases caused by seismic events. Our observations suggest the existence of a strain rate threshold that activates the nonlinear response of the structure, characterizing the activation of cracking and indicating a strong nexus between the elastic structural response, structural state, and the loading process.

KEYWORDS

building response, earthquakes, frequency variations, strain rates

1 | INTRODUCTION

Recent studies have shown that the elastic properties of different systems are significantly modified during strong seismic motions. Fundamental frequency shifts are observed in buildings^{1–4} and seismic velocity changes in the Earth's crust.⁵ These are interpreted by the authors as a co-seismic softening of the medium, linked to the activation of cracks. When loading ceases, the elastic properties begin to recover over time according to a slow dynamic process related to the closing of cracks; this has also been reported by Ostrovsky and Johnson⁶ in rock samples. This recovery is dependent on the level of residual damage.² During the loading phase, the amplitude of shift is generally well correlated with the excitation amplitude, with stronger loadings causing larger shifts. For example, Astorga et al.^{1,2} observed the maximum co-seismic shift of resonance frequencies in buildings to be proportional to maximum structural deformation and peak acceleration. In observations of the Earth, seismic velocity reductions due to earthquake-related processes are also proportional to the excitation amplitude.^{7,8} Similarly, laboratory experiments in rocks and granular media have shown that modulus softening and successive recovery appear to be dependent on both effective loading and duration.^{9–11} Johnson and Jia¹⁰ observed the resonance frequency variation in rock samples as a function of strain, detecting a strain threshold (max. $\sim 10^{-6}$) below which the material behaves in a linear-elastic manner. The resonance frequency shift is therefore dependent on strain for strain values above this threshold. Moreover, Guéguen et al.¹² showed significant nonlinear-elastic behavior in the relationship between frequency variation and strain in buildings under weak and

strong excitations, starting at values as low as $<10^{-5}$, which is well below the typical yield deformation threshold defined for earthquake engineering. Similar behavior is observed in Figure 1A. This figure shows the frequency variations observed in 36 Japanese buildings as a function of the time history of structural drift, computed during two different earthquakes (i.e., one small earthquake and the Mw 9.0 Tohoku event, 2011). In this example, nonlinearity starts at drift values between 10^{-7} and 10^{-6} , that is, three orders of magnitude lower than the yield strain value given for typical buildings. Between-building variability of the response is observed (i.e., ϕ), providing the same distribution of residue for both earthquakes with respect to the fitted linear functions (Figure 1B). Furthermore, considering the same set of buildings for both earthquakes, a given drift value does not imply the same frequency variation, which indicates between-event variability (i.e., τ), as illustrated by the shift between the adjusted functions of the small and large earthquakes. Both types of variability (ϕ and τ) suggest that (1) building response is not governed only by structural typology, and (2) building response is not governed only by loading amplitude. Considering structural drift as a structural proxy of strain, and fundamental frequency as a proxy of the structural elastic properties, the behavior observed differs from the conventional representation of nonlinear models used for structure analysis and is more similar to the typical model for nonlinear elasticity, as demonstrated by laboratory tests and building monitoring.^{10,12}

However, it is well-known that most structural materials used in civil engineering are highly sensitive to the loading process. Properties such as strength, stiffness, and ductility might be strain rate dependent (Bischoff and Perry and Houqun et al.^{13,14}). The strain rate effect is a basic property of the dynamic response of heterogeneous materials, such as concrete. For example, the stiffness of concrete subjected to compression forces can be enhanced at high loading rates. Bischoff and Perry¹³ explained this enhancement by the decrease in internal microcracking, for a given level of stress, as strain rate increases. Furthermore, Johnson and Jia¹⁰ noted that, for equivalent strain amplitudes, the dynamically induced reduction in the elastic modulus was less pronounced than in resonance experiments, concluding that conditioning effects influence modulus softening; this is also seen in diverse systems, including damaged materials.^{9,11} Moreover, previous studies of concrete structures during earthquakes¹⁴ have indicated that the maximum strain rate observed in these cases ranges from 10^{-3} s^{-1} to 10^{-2} s^{-1} . The authors determined that the mechanisms determining strain rate effects are mainly related to thermally activated mechanisms and energy dissipation. Similar conclusions were made by Bischoff and Perry¹³ and Qi et al.,¹⁵ who observed that the low-rate region is controlled by thermal-activated mechanisms. As strain rate increases, there is a transition between the different mechanisms governing the material response: Dissipation mechanisms emerge, gradually becoming dominant, along with inertial effects. Crack density increases, and strain rate sensitivity results from the combined effects of ongoing energy dissipation and the new thermally activated mechanisms. In heterogeneous materials, such as concrete, there might be a critical strain rate above which internal microcracks start to open/close progressively, determining the overall response of the system. Given that strain rates might be important in the dynamic response of structures and that the relationship between structural frequency variations and loading features is still not fully understood, this study evaluates the influence of

FIGURE 1 A, Instantaneous normalized frequency shift ($\Delta f/f = (f - f_i)/f_i$) as a function of structural drift computed for 36 different buildings, during one strong and one weak earthquake. f_i is the pre-seismic fundamental frequency, and f is the frequency computed at each 0.04-s time step. Each marker represents the average of 20 data bins. The dashed lines correspond to the mean response, given by the curve fitting of a 2-term exponential function. Between-building and between-event variabilities are shown by ϕ and τ , respectively. B, Histograms of the errors between the observed response and the fitting function

strain rate on the fundamental frequency variations in buildings during earthquakes. We present two case studies: the ANX building and the THU building, representing different loading amplitudes and damage levels. The dependency of structural response as a function of strain rate is evaluated during loading (i.e., softening, the fundamental frequency decreases, the structure is under conditioning effects) and unloading (i.e., relaxation, the fundamental frequency recovers, loading effects are leaving away), by analyzing the effects of the Mw 9.0 Tohoku earthquake on this relationship.

2 | CASE 1: THE ANX BUILDING

The ANX building is located in Tsukuba, Japan. It is a permanently monitored eight-story steel reinforced-concrete structure, built in 1998. It has recorded a large number of earthquakes over the past 20 years.¹⁶ Maximum structural drift ratio at the top of the building ranges from 10^{-7} to 10^{-3} , with the highest value being triggered during the Tohoku earthquake in 2011, which also caused some visual damage including several cracks in the walls and the rupture of a seismic joint.¹⁷ The transient change in the normalized frequency (i.e., with respect to the pre-seismic fundamental frequency f_i) of the ANX building as a function of structural drift ratio (i.e., maximum relative displacement between the top and the base of the building, obtained by numerical integration of the acceleration data) is shown in Figure 2. The procedure to obtain the instantaneous variations in fundamental frequency (i.e., Wigner–Ville time-frequency distribution) as well as the structural drift ratios is well described in Astorga et al.^{2,16} Figure 2 shows the structural response to several earthquakes recorded within the 5 years prior the Tohoku event. The seismic events are classified according to the maximum drift ratio triggered in the building, $\Delta_{\max}$, as a parameter consistent with loading amplitude.¹⁶ Five ranges of $\Delta_{\max}$ are considered, varying from 1×10^{-6} to 5×10^{-4} as indicated in the plot (Figure 2). The relationship in Figure 2 shows that frequency reductions start at very low values of deformation, around 1×10^{-8} for the smallest events and at 1×10^{-6} in the case of stronger excitation. This is analogous to the observations from Figure 1 and those reported by Johnson and Jia¹⁰ and Guéguen et al.,¹² and represents a distinctive signature of atypical nonlinearity (i.e., nonlinear elasticity) as observed in several materials^{6,18} and building systems.² Moreover, for the same drift value, modulus softening diminishes progressively as loading increases, indicating that the structural response is not governed by the strain (drift ratio) amplitude.

Figure 3 shows the effects of strain rate on the frequency variation during fast loading (i.e., co-seismic transient frequency drop, softening) and recovery (i.e., after loading), observed in the ANX building during earthquakes.^{2,16} The same $\Delta_{\max}$ ranges as in Figure 2 are considered. The responses to earthquakes occurring between 2006 and 2011 (i.e., before the 2011 Tohoku earthquake) and during 2012 (i.e., after the 2011 Tohoku earthquake) are considered, grouped, and averaged. A number of observations can be made about Figure 3:

- The pattern of frequency variations with strain rate during loading differs from that of the recovery regime. Frequency reductions during the loading phase seem to be dependent on strain rate. Regardless of loading amplitude,

FIGURE 2 Instantaneous normalized frequency, $\Delta f/f = (f - f_i)/f_i$, of the ANX building with respect to instantaneous drift ratio, computed every 0.04 s, within the time histories of earthquakes occurring in 2006 and in March 2011. Data are grouped according to the maximum structural deformation ($\Delta 1_{\max}$ – $\Delta 5_{\max}$), and f_i represents the pre-seismic fundamental frequency. The dashed lines correspond to the mean response, obtained by a curve fitting using a 2-term exponential function of the form $a * \exp(b * x) + c * \exp(d * x)$

FIGURE 3 Normalized frequency, $\Delta f/f$, of the ANX building with respect to strain rate during A, loading (frequency decreases) and B, recovery phases during earthquakes. Strain rate is computed as $(\Delta_{i+1} - \Delta_i)/t_s$, with $t_s = 0.04$ s and $\Delta =$ structural drift. (Left) Structural response before the Tohoku earthquake. (Right) Structural response after the Tohoku earthquake. f_i represents the pre-seismic fundamental frequency, and f_f corresponds to the final apparent fundamental frequency observed in the earthquake recordings. The colors represent different loading amplitude ranges in terms of maximum strain, Δ_{max} , as indicated in the legend of the last plot. For (B), the plots should be read from right to left, because in the recovery phase, loading effects are leaving away. The dashed lines correspond to the mean response, obtained by a curve fitting of the form: $a * \exp(b * x) + c * \exp(d * x)$

Δ_{max} , frequency reductions are observed at values around 10^{-7} s^{-1} (Figure 3A—left), representing the activation point of nonlinearities related to the presence of cracks (Houqun et al.¹⁴; Bischoff and Perry and Qi et al.^{13,15}). Above 10^{-7} s^{-1} , as strain rate increases, the fundamental frequency decreases, following the same path for different loading amplitudes (i.e., parallel slopes in $\Delta f/f$ versus strain rate), and reducing between-event variability τ . This result suggests that the transition to a nonlinear response at a strain rate of 10^{-7} s^{-1} implies progressive activation of internal microcracks, causing constant frequency reductions at any loading amplitude.

- The activation strain rate value (10^{-7} s^{-1}) does not change after the Tohoku earthquake (Figure 3A—right). Internal microcracking is still activated at the same strain rate. However, the slope gradient for different loading amplitudes decreases after Tohoku, reaching smaller frequency reductions than before 2011 for the same strain rate. This effect is more obvious for stronger excitation and higher strain rates, implying that the structural response is governed by secondary order factors rather than loading. For example, the distribution of crack size determines stiffness, and the response is more dependent on structural state. As crack density increases, the energy required to activate new cracks (and therefore reduce frequency) increases, as illustrated by the slighter slope after Tohoku (Figure 3A—right). After 2011, the maximum frequency reduction seems to decrease, and this value is not clearly correlated with loading amplitude.
- During the phase of frequency recovery before the Tohoku earthquake (Figure 3B—left), frequency variations with strain rate are quasi parallel for the different loading amplitudes. This indicates the gradual recovery of frequency as conditioning effects decrease. For example, taking the highest excitation levels (i.e., red or yellow curves in Figure 3B—left) and starting with a strain rate of 10^{-4} s^{-1} , the normalized frequency variation is around 0.10; at this strain rate, the structure is still under the effects of conditioning. As the excitation passes, strain rate decreases, as does the frequency variation. At 10^{-5} s^{-1} , $\Delta f/f$ is around 0.02, and at $5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\Delta f/f$ is 0, indicating the end of the

- recovery phase (i.e., relative to the final apparent value, f_f). The same result is observed for all loading amplitudes, with recovery starting at lower strain rates, corresponding to the strength of the event. Recovery rates thus increase as the excitation amplitude increases, which corresponds to observations on laboratory experiments with granular materials.⁶ At strain rates in the order of 10^{-7} s^{-1} , corresponding to noise-rate levels, recovery is complete for any excitation amplitude. This value matches the threshold that activates microcracking during loading (i.e., Figure 3A).
- The 2011 Mw 9.0 earthquake had a number of effects on the frequency recovery as a function of strain rates (Figure 3B—right). Firstly, behavior is less dependent on loading amplitude (i.e., the same behavior is observed for different amplitude ranges, for example, the red and green curves). Secondly, the shape of the $\Delta f/f$ versus strain rate curves has changed, except for the smallest loadings (i.e., black curve) and shows two regimes: At the beginning of the recovery period (i.e., highest strain rates), $\Delta f/f$ varies very quickly with no strain rate variation. Frequency then recovers as strain rate decreases, until the structure is no longer conditioned by shaking, and therefore, $\Delta f/f$ reaches 0 at around 10^{-7} s^{-1} .

Several studies have already proved that elastic property variations in granular materials after dynamic excitation depend on both loading and structural state.^{6,18} In Figures 2 and 3, we observe the effects of loading and loading rate on the reduction and recovery of fundamental frequency in the ANX building. However, Figure 3 also shows that the structural response changes after damaging earthquakes, causing frequency variations less sensitive to loading features and more closely related to the current state of cracking within the structural material. These observations correspond to the ANX building, considered to have been slightly damaged by the 2011 Tohoku event.¹⁷ The effects of more severe damage are observed in Figure 4, which shows frequency variations as a function of strain rate during loading and recovery (similar to Figure 3) for another structure: the THU building.

3 | CASE 2: THE THU BUILDING

The THU building is located in Tohoku, Japan. It is a permanently instrumented nine-story, steel reinforced-concrete structure built in 1969 and significantly repaired and retrofitted in 2000–2001.¹⁹ Since the retrofit, the building has

FIGURE 4 Same as Figure 3 for the THU building

experienced several significant earthquakes causing considerable acceleration and high drift values. The great earthquake in 2011 triggered the maximum drift ratio at the top of the building, 1.06×10^{-2} , which is close to the threshold defined for severe damage in this type of building (i.e., 1.17×10^{-2} , according to FEMA²⁰). Significant variations in the fundamental period of the structure were observed after the 2011 event, together with considerable damage reported by Kashima et al.²¹ and Celebi et al. based on post-seismic observations. This included four heavily crushed columns and severe cracking in the shear walls. The loading history of the THU building and its dynamic behavior has been analyzed by Motosaka et al.,²² Motosaka and Mitsuji,²³ and Kashima et al.²¹ The levels of excitation experienced by this structure include drift ratios that are one order of magnitude higher than those of the ANX building. As in Figure 3, variations of fundamental frequency as a function of structural drift ratio are shown in Figure 4 for the THU building during several earthquakes occurring before and after the great earthquake in 2011. The lowest range of loading amplitudes (i.e., $\Delta_{\max}$) in Figure 4 is equivalent to the $\Delta_{3\max}$ of Figure 3, denoting the high excitation levels experienced by the THU building over its lifespan. This is also shown by the lowest strain rate computed, around 10^{-7} s^{-1} . Frequency variations start to become dependent on strain rate at $\sim 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (i.e., the vertical dashed lines in Figure 4A) for any loading amplitude, confirming the existence of a threshold that determines the transition between linear and nonlinear behavior. However, the level of cracking in the THU building causes frequency variations to appear at a higher strain rate value, 10^{-5} s^{-1} (compared with 10^{-7} s^{-1} in ANX), confirming that more energy is required to change the current state of a material that is already cracked. The building's response during loading changed after 2011, showing faster frequency reductions, which might be related to the substantial increase in the density of existing cracks. The energy required to propagate an existing crack is much less than the energy required to open a new crack. Therefore, the energy (i.e., strain rate) necessary to cause a certain frequency reduction after 2011 is less than the energy needed to cause the same frequency reduction before 2011. This implies that the already cracked structure (i.e., before 2011) suffered a significant increase in existing cracks, because of its high susceptibility to cracking activation at lower energy levels, thus explaining the steeper gradient of the slopes in Figure 4A—right. In the recovery phase (Figure 4B), high frequency recovery rates are observed, reaching $\Delta f/f = 0$ at strain rates between 10^{-5} s^{-1} and 10^{-4} s^{-1} . Steep recovery slopes are typically observed in damaged materials^{6,24} because there are more cracks, and internal particles in the material move quickly to fill them, driven by nonlinear-elastic processes dependent on both loading and damage level.²

4 | CONCLUSIONS

Frequency variations are dependent on both loading features (i.e., strain amplitude and strain rate) and structural state. We observed that softening (i.e., a decrease in fundamental frequency due to a decrease in modulus) increases as loading values increase (Figure 2). The variations observed in the elastic property are mainly due to transient and permanent changes in structural stiffness, which is determined by the density of cracks creating weaknesses in the structural material. As the density of cracks (i.e., damage) increases, the structural response is less dependent on loading features and more governed by the degree of cracking. The structural response becomes more complex and more difficult to predict using loading parameters, which is typical in nonlinear behavior. On the other hand, structural response seems to be more sensitive to strain rates than to strain amplitudes. Strain amplitudes determine the maximum frequency variation Δf , whereas strain rates determine the behavior of frequency variations during loading and recovery periods, reducing the between-event variability of the building response, which is a key issue in performance engineering and structural analysis. The behavior of frequency variations with strain rates differs during loading and recovery periods. During loading, a threshold defines nonlinear behavior, that is, the activation of cracks. During the recovery period, frequency variations decrease as conditioning effects decrease, and higher excitation amplitudes result in faster recovery rates. Finally, we found a threshold defining strain rate dependence during loading. It is around 10^{-7} s^{-1} in slightly cracked media and increases to 10^{-5} s^{-1} in densely cracked materials, indicating the larger amount of energy needed to cause structural response variations in damaged media.

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